

TRANSFORMATION OF VEGETATION COVER IN THE OHANGARON RIVER BASIN

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Abstract

The transformation some community of the vegetation of Ahangaran basin is brought in isolated type in proposed article. Their degrees and mechanisms of transformations under influence of biotical, abiotical and anthropogenic factors are conducted in the work. The work was executed by cartographic inventory and got results can be used for fight with desertification, as well as revision of the restoration way of rare disappearing species in the removal region

Keywords: transformation, map, vegetable cover, flora, ecology, protection of vegetation, air cosmic, bio spectrum.

Introduction

Ensuring the economically sustainable development of the Republic of Uzbekistan largely depends on the rational use of natural resources, including plant resources, as well as on maintaining the historically established balance of raw material potential and using it efficiently and effectively.

Based on this, identifying the current state of vegetation cover in certain natural-geographical regions, determining the level of its transformation through mapping methods, and developing necessary recommendations are among the urgent tasks.

The current state of vegetation cover in the Ohangaron River basin is the result of long-term anthropogenic impacts.

The Ohangaron basin is one of the largest basins (5,260 km²) located on the southwestern slopes of the Tien Shan mountain system. It includes all altitudinal zones found in Uzbekistan: desert (266–500 m), foothill (500–1500 m), mountain (1500–2500 m), and alpine pasture (2500–4062 m), each representing ecosystems with their own unique biospectrum. In the works of the above-mentioned authors, plant types, their descriptions, and characteristics are presented within the context of the Tien Shan, Tashkent region, and the Chirchiq–Ohangaron basins.

Our research in the Ohangaron basin revealed that nearly all types of vegetation characteristic of these zones are present. However, their distribution boundaries, composition, and structure have undergone varying degrees of transformation and degradation (desertification) due to numerous anthropogenic factors.

In the vegetation map of the Ohangaron basin (scale 1:200,000) developed by us, degraded areas are indicated with indices (A, B, C).

In the Ohangaron basin, almost all types of anthropogenic factors are present: large geological quarries, roads, reservoirs, industrial plants, deforestation, unregulated harvesting of medicinal and aromatic plants, an increase in livestock numbers, and fodder collection activities—all of which contribute to the degradation of vegetation cover. Comparative analysis of data plays an important role in determining the degree of vegetation transformation.

The study of transformed vegetation was mainly carried out by comparing data with S.N. Kudryashev's "Vegetation Cover of Ohangaron" map (scale

1:200,000, 1942) and E.P. Korovin's "Vegetation Cover of Central Asia" map (scale 1:1,000,000, 1956).

When comparing the current ecological condition of certain plant communities in the Ohangaron basin with data from Kudryashev's 1942 map, it was found that a 150-hectare area from Akcha village to Suvzamchi—consisting of *Carex pachystylis* and *Poa bulbosa* communities with sparse pistachio trees (*Pistacia vera*)—has undergone transformation. Similarly, riparian forests between Ohangaron and Turk village, including willow (*Salix wilhelmsiana*) and poplar (*Populus densa*), have also been transformed.

It was also determined that of the 9,980 hectares of juniper forests in the upper part of the Ohangaron basin, only 4,360 hectares remain today.

According to the map of S.N. Kudryashev, pistachio woodlands are identified in the Akhangaran basin area. These pistachio stands (*Pistacia vera*) are distributed along the right bank of the Akhangaran River basin, around Kaynar, Karakhitoy, Toshbulok, Akcha, Koytosh, Baksuk, and Chetsu.

Pistachio communities (*Pistacia vera* L.) are found from Karaboshsoy to Chetsu within broadleaf forests, in small quantities mixed with juniper, hawthorn (*Crataegus pontica*), and wild almond (*Amygdalus petunnikowii*). In this area, pistachio stands cover 52.52 km².

In the regions of Kaynar, Karakhitoy, and Chilmakhrom, pistachio (*Pistacia vera*) occurs within communities dominated by sedge (*Carex pachystylis*) and bulbous bluegrass (*Poa bulbosa*), along with perennial xerophytic ephemeroïds and sparse juniper woodlands. Pistachio stands occupy 41.8 km² in Kaynar, 11.2 km² in Karakhitoy, and 3.6 km² in the upper part of Angren around Chilmakhrom.

Between Kaynar and Karakhitoy in the Akhangaran area, sparse pistachio stands within sedge–bluegrass communities (*Carex pachystylis* – *Poa bulbosa*) have completely disappeared as a result of cultivation. The degree of transformation in this area reaches 100%.

On the left bank of the Akhangaran, in the Kurama Mountains from Akcha to Suzamchi, pistachio (*Pistacia vera*) grows among sedge–bluegrass (*Carex pachystylis* – *Poa bulbosa*) communities with perennial xerophytic ephemerals, covering 42 km². From Urgoz to the village of Turk, pistachio stands mixed with juniper within broadleaf forests occupy 48.5 km².

In the area from Kara-Tyube to Mirza-Kul, mixed forests contain pistachio along with juniper, walnut (*Juglans regia* L.), apple (*Malus sieversii* (Led.) M. Roem.), and wild cherry (*Prunus sogdiana* Vass.), covering 39.4 km².

At present, pistachio woodlands have almost disappeared due to both natural and anthropogenic factors. Natural factors include mudflows and soil erosion, while the main anthropogenic impact is the cutting of pistachio trees for use as fuel.

According to the data from the “Vegetation Map of Central Asia” (scale 1:1,000,000) created by E.P. Korovin in 1956, a comparison with the current state shows that 120 hectares of narrow-leaved wormwood vegetation (*Artemisia ferganensis*) around Kokorol village, as well as 120 hectares of bluegrass (*Poa bulbosa*) and sedge (*Carex pachystylis*) communities in the area from Shovozsoy to its confluence with the Ohangaron River, have disappeared.

It was also found that of the mixed tugai forests, only 40 hectares remain out of 4,500 hectares; of the 540 hectares of wheatgrass (*Agropyron trichophorum*) vegetation between Boyaul and Shovvozsoy, only 36 hectares remain; and of the 185

hectares of ephemeral vegetation around Kokorol village, only 13.3 hectares remain. These areas have been developed and converted for economic use.

Additionally, it was determined that species such as walnut (*Juglans regia*), apple (*Malus sieversii*), and hawthorn (*Crataegus pontica*) have also undergone a certain degree of transformation in the studied region.

On the right bank of the Ohangaron River—in Cholibosh, the upper parts of Akchasoy, Karabogsoy, tributaries of Dukentsoy, and around Irtosh—walnut (*Juglans regia*) and apple (*Malus sieversii*), along with perennial herbaceous plants, juniper (*Juniperus seravschanica*), and wild cherry (*Prunus sogdiana*), are distributed as part of mixed broadleaf forest vegetation, covering an area of 157 km². Naturally occurring walnut (*Juglans regia*) and apple (*Malus sieversii*) are found in the upper reaches of Shavvozsoy, Akchasoy, Karaboysoy, Dukentsoy, and Kizilsoy, as well as in the areas between Akchasoy and Kizilsoy. On the left bank of the river, they are distributed in the Kurama Mountains around Shougazsoy, Obiyazsoy, Gushsoy, Kushrabotsoy, Lashkereksoy, Gushsoy, and Kamchiksoy. They are also found at the confluence points of Kamchiksoy, Turkshumsoy, and Mirzaqulsoy with the Ohangaron River.

On the left bank of the Ohangaron, within the Kurama mountain range, walnut (*Juglans regia*) and apple (*Malus sieversii*) occupy an area of 138 km². In the Chatkal and Kurama mountains, walnut and apple forests covered 295 km².

At present, due to anthropogenic and natural factors, the areas occupied by walnut (*Juglans regia*) and apple (*Malus sieversii*) have significantly decreased.

Hawthorn (*Crataegus pontica*) is distributed in the Chatkal Range from Qaynar to Chetsu, and in the Kurama Range from Akcha to the village of Turk,

within mixed broadleaf forests and on stony-gravelly soils together with almond (*Amygdalus spinosissima*), pistachio (*Pistacia vera*), and juniper (*Juniperus zeravschanica*). It is also found in communities of ephemeroïds such as *Carex pachystylis* and *Poa bulbosa*, as well as among perennial xerophytes, and occasionally in pistachio and almond woodlands.

Hawthorn is widespread in the areas of Karaboshsoy, Toshbuloq, Juvoxona, Akcha, Qoytosh, and Baksuk as part of broadleaf tree and shrub communities, covering an area of 114.1 km². On the left bank of the Ohangaron River, hawthorn populations extend from Urgoz to the village of Turk, occupying 81.18 km².

Willow (*Salix wilhelmsiana*) and poplar (*Populus densa*) are widely distributed in riparian (tugai) forests along the Ohangaron River and its tributaries, particularly along the banks of Karaboshsoy, Shovassoy, Akchasoy, Qarabausoy, Dukentsoy, and Chetsu, as well as in areas on the left bank of the Ohangaron such

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s Naugorzansoy, Larek, Lashkareksay, and Qamchiqsoy. They are also common in the tugai forests of the Ohangaron River from the city of Ohangaron to the village of Turk.

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, At present, however, the area occupied by tugai forests—particularly willow (*Salix wilhelmsiana*) and poplar (*Populus densa*)—is sharply decreasing. The main reason for this is the expansion of human activity into tugai areas, as well as the cutting of willows and poplars for construction materials and fuel.

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The vegetation cover of the studied region is undergoing significant changes under the influence of both natural and anthropogenic factors. It is essential to preserve the vegetation cover and maintain its current state without drastic alteration. To prevent further degradation, it is necessary to consider the Ohangaron basin as a single integrated unit and to determine the patterns of vegetation distribution by zones, its typological structure, phytocenotic diversity, dynamic state, degree of degradation, and the types of anthropogenic factors causing this degradation. This is one of the most pressing issues today.

For this reason, studies were conducted (between 2000 and 2015) using a combination of traditional geobotanical and mapping methods to assess the distribution of plant types in the Ohangaron basin, their phytocenotic diversity, and transformation processes.

The results of these studies play an important role in providing a comprehensive inventory of the dynamic state of plant communities in the studied basin, ensuring their efficient use, planning reconstruction of areas requiring protection, and preserving the gene pool of the region

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